

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: *ZZAZZ*

Generating a Trust Index for
News Publishers

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1 Executive Summary

The challenge consists of deriving a trust index that represents the credibility of a news article publisher's trustworthiness and its audience engagement/revenue. The primary goal is to create a system that assigns a trust index to publishers. This index should reflect the overall credibility and reliability of the information they publish, while also exploring the relationship between the trust index and audience engagement.

The dataset was provided by ZZAZZ, an AI economics research and development company that uses cutting-edge deep learning algorithms to dynamically price every piece of internet content¹. It consists of article features from 32 publishers, covering a time period from 2019 to 2022. These features included bias, sentiment, and audience engagement. The dataset was supplemented by a relative rankings list of all these publishers at the end of 2022, representing the credibility of publishers based on open-source reports and ZZAZZ's in-house journalist team.

After exploring the data, we chose an auto-regressive (AR) model as the simplest representation of a time-varying process. A trust index is assumed to depend on the history of its performance, as prior untrustworthy behaviour would influence users' opinions on a publisher's current trustworthiness. For the causal analysis, we began with a simple bivariate time series causal discovery and performed a causal effect estimation step.

The analysis demonstrates that bias and objectivity scores are the best features for predicting publisher rankings across different temporal aggregations. On average, a publisher's data from the last month is highly correlated with the given Trust Index. There are causal relationships between content quality and user engagement, but this relationship is heterogeneous and dynamic over time. Therefore, the choice of model needs to be validated, as we believe the Trust Index should dynamically adjust over time and be more granular than just the publisher level, incorporating specific article types and categories.

Future work can focus on refining validation methods for assessing

¹At the time of the DSG ZZAZZ was called Kunato.AI

“trustworthiness” in data-scientific approaches. This includes integrating broader external validation data and domain expertise to establish formal definitions of trust. Addressing temporal dynamics will be crucial to capture changes in trust over time. Full-text analysis could provide intuitive validation by correlating the constructed trust index with linguistic patterns typical of unreliable sources.

2 Introduction

The aim of this Data Study Group (DSG) challenge is to develop a framework based on machine learning that can derive a trust index for the news articles of different publishers, and to develop a system that can be used to understand the relationship between trust index and user engagement. This trust index will be a culmination of Machine Learning (ML)-derived factors representing credibility.

The challenge owner is ZZAZZ. ZZAZZ is an AI economics research and development company that utilizes advanced deep learning algorithms to dynamically price internet content, thereby creating a new market for information commerce. The company aims to quantify the value of information, enhance content delivery, boost revenue for creators, and improve the overall transparency in the digital landscape. ZZAZZ’s goal is to create a system which could effectively filter publishers, enhancing the transparency and reliability of online content. At the minimum, the challenge set out to create a basic trust index for ZZAZZ to enable more informed content valuation and to further uncover the link between trust index and audience engagement. This understanding would allow predicting the potential impact on publisher traffic based on changes in their trust index. Building on these findings, ZZAZZ could fully integrate the trust index into their existing content valuation system, and use it to simulate the impact of changes in certain features on publisher traffic and revenue metrics, allowing them to filter publishers and provide valuable feedback to them. It could be the starting point for a new standard within ZZAZZ for content trustworthiness and evaluation.

2.1 Background

Due to the abundance of fake content, the digital landscape is becoming increasingly complex. Currently, individuals rely on various sources to assess publisher credibility, making this task impractical for users due to the extensive research and manual effort involved. The shift towards choosing news based on trust rather than popularity is crucial for creating a more reliable online information environment. In other words, people should focus on credible sources instead of just what is popular.

For publishers, this could demonstrate that audience trust directly impacts revenue. Publishers who prioritise transparency and reduce misinformation could benefit from increased audience trust, leading to higher engagement and revenue. This involves two interconnected problem statements: obtaining a trust index for publishers and understanding how this index relates to user engagement and revenue.

The trust index offers a standardised measure of a publisher's credibility, providing users with a comprehensive and qualitative assessment of publishers, moving beyond subjective perceptions or scattered information sources. Having a trust index can guide users in selecting reputable publishers based on their track record of quality journalism, minimal misinformation, unbiased language, and overall credibility, eliminating the need for individual research efforts with each news piece.

2.2 Data Study Group Objectives

This Data Study Group challenge aims to significantly improve transparency among publishers, combat the spread of fake news, and help create a more reliable and trustworthy online content environment. The central objective is: "Can we develop a Trust Index for publishers and use it to predict how much readers who trust a publisher will engage with their content?" This encompasses the following tasks:

- Deriving a trust index representing the credibility of the publisher.
- Analysing the relationship between the trust index and user engagement.

3 Data Overview

3.1 Dataset Description

The dataset provided by ZZAZZ consists of the following:

- A zipped folder with 32 Parquet files for each publisher, which consists of 18 features on the articles published.
- A CSV file for the rankings of all 32 publishers at the end of 2022. This is the relative ranking representing the credibility of the publishers using open-source reports and in-house journalist team.

Upon combining all Parquet files together, we have data spanning December 2019 to December 2023, and 581004 articles in total.

The article-level data has been divided into features derived by ZZAZZ's team:

- Publisher ID – Unique ID representing publisher (string)
- Article ID – Unique ID representing article (string)
- Author ID – Unique ID representing author (string)
- Article Published Date - Article's published date (date)
- Bias – Indicates the presence of bias in the text (string) (Neutral/ Slightly Bias/ Highly Bias)
- Sentiment – Indicates the overall sentiment of the news (String) (Positive/ Neutral/ Negative)
- Clickbait – Indicates whether the title for the news is a clickbait (integer) where 0 represents clickbait absent, and 1 represents clickbait present
- Number of quotes – Number of times personalities or Authorities are quoted in the text (integer)
- Number of unique links – Number of unique references to other news/sources in the text (integer)
- Category - Category the news belongs to (string). The possible categories are one of 20: military, finance, politics, law and order,

health, entertainment, economy, art and culture, environment, education, technology, sports, food and drink, weather, travel and transportation, religion, astronomy, business, language and wildlife.

- Bias and Objectivity Score – Score derived based on other features and using expert indicators. A higher score indicates a more objective and less biased article (continuous feature 0-100)
- Text vector – 786 length vector representing the article text (array)
- Overall engagement score - Audience engagement impressions per article (float) where a higher score represents higher engagement
- Positive engagement score - Possible values between [0,1](float) where a higher score represents more positive engagement
- Negative engagement score - Possible values between [0,1] (float) where a higher score represents more negative engagement
- Neutral engagement score - Possible values between [0,1] (float) where a higher score represents more neutral engagement
- News alleged fake - Binary feature representing the presence of engagement alleging the content as fake news where 0 means not alleged fake and 1 means alleged fake.
- Discussion Score - Discussion-based engagement on the article (float) with possible values between [0,100] where higher values indicate the article invokes and invites more discussion among the public.
- News acknowledgement Score - Represents the explicit engagement by the public using comments, sharing etc. A higher score indicates higher explicit engagement.

In table 1, we present an overview of the data, including the number of entries and data type of each data attribute.

3.2 Data Quality

In this section, we discuss the quality of the data we are working with. Mougan *et al.*) [8] suggest examining the following aspects of data quality,

Table 1: Overview of the combined dataset

	Column	Non-Null Count	Dtype
0	publisher_id	581004 non-null	object
1	article_id	581004 non-null	object
2	author_id	222812 non-null	object
3	article_published_date	581004 non-null	object
4	article_bias	581004 non-null	object
5	article_sentiment	581004 non-null	object
6	article_clickbait_flag	581004 non-null	int64
7	article_num_quotes	581004 non-null	int64
8	article_num_links	581004 non-null	int64
9	article_category	581004 non-null	object
10	bias_and_objectivity_score	581004 non-null	float64
11	article_vector	581004 non-null	object
12	overall_engagement_score	581004 non-null	float64
13	positive_engagement_pct	519199 non-null	float64
14	negative_engagement_pct	519199 non-null	float64
15	neutral_engagement_pct	519199 non-null	float64
16	news_alleged_fake	581004 non-null	int64
17	discussion_score	581004 non-null	float64
18	news_acknowledgement_score	519199 non-null	float64

which is summarised in table 2 for this challenge:

- **Appropriateness:** Data is appropriate for the challenge, however the article features can notably be enhanced with data that ZAZZ could provide. For example, it would be beneficial to have access to the article text, rather than solely the text embedding vectors, or some further knowledge on how these vectors were created. Additionally, having the publisher ranking at the last timestamp (end of 2022) posed some limitations for the analysis. If publisher ranking had been present at all timestamps, it would have transformed the challenge into a supervised learning problem, which could have been more straightforward.
- **Readiness:** Data is collated, clean, and with minimal missing/NA values. The data is also documented with the data dictionary and

data cards.

- **Reliability:** Data has known biases that will impact the analysis and can be corrected or accounted for as a work limitation. For example, the way the 32 publishers are selected is not known. Additionally, there is an imbalance in the representation of categories. There are some article categories that are skewed, which could mean that our final model works better for some categories like politics, law and order and health, which are sufficiently represented.
- **Sensitivity:** There were limited risks associated with the data, usually publicly available data. Original user comments were converted to features to protect identities.
- **Sufficiency:** The data was sufficient, as there were 32 publishers.

Table 2: Summary of our data quality assessment for the five data dimensions as defined in Mogan *et al.* (2023) [8].

Dimension	Definition	Insufficient	Developing	Functional	Optimal
Appropriateness	Was the data relevant to the questions posed?				
Readiness	Is the data complete, is there relevant metadata available, and is there sufficient data documentation?				
Reliability	To what extent do the data accurately represent the population or phenomenon?				
Sensitivity	Was the data private or confidential?				
Sufficiency	Was the amount of data enough?				

3.3 Data Pre-processing

3.3.1 For the auto-regressive model

All entries with "N/A" were removed, while all categorical data were pre-processed by one-hot encoding. Specifically for each data category, under a one-hot encoding, each category value becomes a new binary category. For instance, the variable "article_category" has 20 possible values such as "politics", "health" and "law and order". Under the one-hot encoding, the singular categorical variable "article_category" then becomes 20 binary variables such as "article_category_politics" and "article_category_health".

3.3.2 For time series methods

An important step in data processing is aggregating article-level observations into time series variables. The granularity of aggregation is a critical analytical decision, as it will affect the balance between signal and noise in the aggregated time series variable, which will, in turn, significantly impact any downstream analysis. Importantly, there are some bias-variance trade-offs to consider. For example, a higher level of aggregation, resulting in a coarser time series variable, can filter out some of the high-frequency noise in article-level observations, thereby improving the precision of downstream analysis. However, if the time interval of measurement is too coarse, it may introduce measurement error into the variable, which will bias the downstream analysis.

Similarly, assuming that the dynamics between content quality and user engagement are heterogeneous across article categories and publishers, constructing time series variables for content attributes separately for each publisher*article-category would make the results of downstream analysis more interpretable and less likely to be biased by confounding. On the other hand, given a fixed sample size (and sample density over time), more disaggregated time series would result in fewer individual observation points per time period, leading to a noisier time series variable and greater variance in downstream analysis.

In this project specifically, we constructed:

- i. time series variables at daily intervals and for each publisher*article-

category

- ii. time series variables at weekly intervals for each publisher
- iii. time series variables at weekly intervals for each article category.

However, the dataset provided does not support variable construction (i) at sufficient quality. While variable construction (ii) would better align with the part 1 and part 2 objectives of the project, we ultimately proceeded with variable construction (iii), as exploratory analysis indicates that the relationship between article objectivity and user engagement varies more significantly across categories than across publishers.

3.4 Exploratory Data Analysis

3.4.1 Clustering on Text-Embedding of Articles

Textual data – i.e. the actual content – of each article is embedded into a 768-dimensional vector space. Given such high-dimensional vectors, visualisation requires projection into principal components, specifically restricted to two components for clearer illustration.

During the exploration stage, we attempted a few different approaches to cluster the point cloud (each point representing an article) to understand whether there was any correspondence between the text-embedding space to the other features, namely: 1) category of article, 2) publisher, 3) bias and objectivity score. Figure 1 shows the point cloud projected into the 2D principal component space, with three different colourings based on the three features.

Figure 1: Projection of the article vectorisation point cloud for 5% (29051) of the articles, into the first two principle components, with three different colourings representing: 1) category of article (left), 2) publisher (middle) and 3) bias and objectivity score (right).

Given the lack of visually obvious clustering via the three colourings we then attempted K-means clustering to identify k clusters within the point cloud. As k is not *a priori* known, we looked at the inertia (the sum of squared errors between each point and their respective nearest cluster-centroid) for each k -sized clustering, and identify a good k via the elbow method. As shown in fig. 2 the inertia does not significantly drop at any specific $k \leq 40$, implying the number of clusters will be more than 40. As this number is greater than both the number of article categories and number of publishers, we deemed this approach a failure.

Figure 2: A plot of the inertia (sum of squared mean distances to the centroid) for various number of clusters.

3.4.2 Cosine Similarities of Text-Embedding of Articles

An alternative perspective to understanding whether there was a link between the text-embedding vector space and the bias and objectivity score was to calculate the pairwise cosine similarities for all vectors and compare this to the pairwise differences between scores. Our hypothesis is based on the bias and objectivity score as a potential proxy for a trust index metric. This means if there are significant similarities between the text embeddings (i.e. the cosine similarities) and the differences in scores between articles, then the text embeddings are a significant feature in determining a trust index. To test this theory, we randomly selected 1000 articles from one publisher and calculate the pairwise cosine similarities between all text vectors. Cosine similarity is a dot product normalised by vectors' magnitudes

$$sim_{\cos}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y}}{\|\mathbf{x}\| \times \|\mathbf{y}\|}. \quad (1)$$

This is one metric for measuring the distance between vectors, more specifically eq. (1) is equal to the cosine between two vectors. The closer the vectors are, the higher the metric value. Our hypothesis is that the higher the metric values are, the closer the bias and objectivity score is for those articles. In other words, there is some correlation between the differences in text vectors and the differences in scores. The cosine distances are stored in a 1000 by 1000 matrix for this sample data. Then we use t-SNE (t-distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding) to reduce the high dimensionality of the data in order to visualise our cosine distances [15].

Figure 3: A t-SNE representation of the cosine distances for 1000 randomly selected articles from one publisher, coloured by bias and objectivity score.

From fig. 3 there does not appear to be any clustering among the bias and objectivity score and the cosine similarities. However, when calculating the pairwise differences between the bias and objectivity scores for all entries within that sample, we find that the Pearson correlation coefficient is approximately 0.2, with a p-value close to zero. This suggests an extremely weak positive correlation. However, the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant, meaning it is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance alone.

To identify where this significance may lie, we investigated the average cosine similarities across all publishers, for different months. The published articles span across four years, which includes the COVID-19 period and other significant global events. It was observed in fig. 4 that the scores were highest on average during 2022. Pairwise cosine similarities were computed for each month in 2022 to explore any potential correlation between these and the bias and objectivity scores. Our hypothesis is that peaks in scores may align with important or shocking events, which many articles will report on. In other words, we expect that article similarity (and, by proxy, cosine similarity) will increase when a global event occurs, as more articles cover the same topics.

Figure 4: A time series plot of the average bias and objectivity score across all publishers in each month.

To give more intuition to these types of global events, we explore the number of articles which are published in different category types (fig. 5). Looking then solely at the most common article categories, we can relate this intuitively to such events. For example, the peak in health articles in

March 2022 aligns with the outbreak of COVID-19, and the delayed peak in law and order articles could align with lockdown and COVID-19 related policies. However, without further analysis of the linguistic or textual data, we cannot confirm whether this is the case.

Figure 5: The number of articles published under different categories, as defined the data, per month for all years.

Figure 6: The number of Health, Military, Law & Order and Politics articles, published per month for all years.

The cosine similarities were calculated for each month across all years for the three most common article categories; Health, Politics and Law & Order, as shown in fig. 7. This is to investigate whether this earlier statistical significance comes from a link between the article category and the similarity of the text embeddings. The pairwise cosine similarities were measured and averaged over all article-article pairs. We observe how the cosine similarities vary over time, particularly the cosine similarities for health articles generally increase over time. This suggests we see a higher number of similar health articles over time. However, this is not supported by our findings in fig. 6, where the higher number of health articles (likely to be reporting on COVID-19) is not signalled in the cosine similarity calculations.

Figure 7: The average of pairwise cosine similarities over all articles published per month, for Health, Politics and Law & Order articles.

However, plotting the cosine similarities by category against their average bias and objectivity score (fig. 8) we do see again this weak positive correlation. Therefore, although this is not strongly correlated with the scores, this gives evidence that there is some underlying importance within the text embeddings such that we should use this as a feature within our models.

Relationship between Cosine Similarity and Bias and Objectivity Score by Article Category

Figure 8: A scatter plot to show the relationship between the average bias and objectivity scores and the cosine similarities, for Health, Politics and Law & Order article categories.

3.4.3 Feature Importance

A model was trained to predict bias and objectivity score. The model was then used to compute the importance of features using two criteria:

- All features excluding the text-embedding vectors
- All features including the text-embedding vectors

Firstly, we consider all features of the data except from the text-embedding vectors. We observed that the feature with the most importance was Overall Engagement, as shown in fig. 9.

Figure 9: Feature importance based on random forest without article vectors

Additionally, feature importance was computed while also including the text-embedding vectors for the articles. In this case, the text-embedding vector and the number of links were of the highest importance.

From the results from the random forest regression the Mean Squared Error (MSE) for all features without the article embedding was 82.3 and with the article vectors included was 5.4.

3.4.4 Spearman's Rank Correlation

To evaluate the performance of different features in predicting the rankings of publishers, we performed a series of analyses comparing predicted rankings to those provided by expert reviewers. We employed

Table 3: Comparison of MSE values without article vectors and with article vectors

	Without article vectors	With article vectors
MSE	82.3	5.4

Spearman’s rank correlation to measure the alignment between the predicted and actual rankings. We first evaluated how well the Spearman correlation fitted to the ranking comparison task (fig. 10)

Figure 10: Distribution of Spearman correlations between the ground truth ranking and 1000 random rankings.

Since the publisher expert ranking was only available at the last time step,

we aimed to identify the feature in the data that best approximates the publisher ranking across all time periods without adequate domain knowledge. The data was aggregated by publisher, calculating both the total and average values for each feature chosen by the random forest process. Publishers were then ranked based on these average values using a dense ranking method, ensuring that higher average values received higher ranks. These new rankings were subsequently merged with an existing ranking dataset, and Spearman's rank correlation was computed to assess the alignment between each feature-based ranking and the existing system. Even in this overall analysis, the bias and objectivity scores remained the top predictors of the expert rankings, as shown in fig. 11. This analysis demonstrates that the bias and objectivity score is the best feature for approximating the publisher expert rankings at the last time step. This allowed us to use the random forest to select the best features that can predict the bias and objectivity score.

Figure 11: Comparison of generated ranking with various features and the expert ranking for news publishers on full dataset

4 Approach

4.1 Research Questions

Our two research questions are:

1. Can we develop a trust index for publishers that dynamically changes over time?
2. Does a higher trust index (or bias and objectivity score) lead to more positive user engagement?

4.2 Problem Statement

Given the set of articles $\mathcal{A} = \{a_0, a_1, \dots\}$ published by a set of publishers $\mathcal{P} = \{p_0, p_1, \dots\}$, we want to build the trust index of each publisher $p \in P$, $X^p(t)$ at time t . Then, we want to explore whether this index, or some form of its proxy, has a causal impact on user engagement.

4.3 Scientific Approach

The main approach used in the analysis is illustrated in (fig. 12), which consists of auto-regressive modelling and causal modelling.

4.3.1 Auto-regressive modelling approaches

After exploring the data, we chose an auto-regressive (AR) model as the simplest representation of a time-varying process. An AR model predicts the current value of a time series as a linear combination of its past values plus a random error term, making it intuitive and interpretable. A trust index is assumed to depend on the history of its performance, as prior untrustworthy behaviour would influence users' opinions on current trustworthiness. The dynamic nature of the trust index necessitates a time series model, further supporting the choice of an auto-regressive model.

The formalisation of this problem meant it was not possible to use a supervised learning approach. Our only validation possibility was the publisher ranking derived from the final time step of the feature examples,

which provided a single sample for validation—a one-shot learning problem. In the context of our auto-regressive setup, where weight optimisation plays a crucial role in enhancing model performance, several approaches were considered, including Bayesian optimisation, stochastic gradient descent, and grid search. Due to the one-shot nature of the problem, we opted for a comprehensive grid search.

This method could then be validated by back-predicting through the dataset to derive the trust index for previous time steps. It is expected that ZZZZ has data to generate publisher rankings at various time steps. Our framework is therefore deployable at any time step, allowing us to generate a distribution for each publisher, charting their trustworthiness over time, as well as the overall trustworthiness of news at a given point in time.

The inability to formalise a supervised learning approach led to a second work stream, which attempted to map the publisher rank relationship to the article feature space.

4.3.2 Causal modelling approaches

Part two of the problem focused on how trustworthiness of content impacts user engagement. Research question 2 can be approached either as a causal discovery problem or a causal inference problem.

From a causal discovery point of view, while existing literature has offered lots of insight into trust and user engagement, we do not have perfect theoretical knowledge of the underlying causal processes to articulate them as mechanistic models with rigorous causal interpretations, specific to the given time frame and the context of the Indian media market. Therefore, in response to the research question, a data-driven approach is called for to flush out potentially robust causal relations in the set of variables provided. The strength of the causal discovery perspective is that it encourages exploratory analysis and open-ended findings.

From a canonical causal inference perspective, research question 2 can be interpreted as a hypothesis that more trustworthy content attracts more user engagement. This approach requires the design and construction of a (semi)experimental setup based on observational data to test the hypothesis. While this form of hypothesis testing is powerful

and intuitive, we must also acknowledge the complex and dynamic nature of market interactions. Empirically, the answer to research question 2 will vary over time and across different sub-markets in terms of content type and user type. Therefore, to answer the question rigorously and provide actionable insights for real business settings, the hypothesis testing would need to be repeated across different market contexts. This, in turn, would transform the hypothesis testing exercise into a naive causal discovery exercise.

Given these considerations, in this project, we combined two stages of causal analysis: (1) starting with a simple bivariate time series causal discovery to detect patterns of directed dependence between content objectivity and user engagement across sub-markets, and (2) zooming in on a specific setting to test and estimate causal effects.

Respectively, mainstream methods are selected in the two stages of causal analysis.

1. Causal Discovery Step: We use transfer entropy to test for dependence between time series of user engagement metrics and content bias-objectivity scores across sub-markets. While the objectivity score may not precisely reflect trustworthiness at the publisher level, modelling at a granular level can reveal more information about the underlying complex market interactions.
2. Causal Effect Estimation Step: We focus on the sub-market of 'politics' articles, using matching techniques to construct comparable groups of observations in order to estimate the effect of content objectivity on user engagement scores.

4.4 Methods

4.4.1 Auto-regressive Models

We take a standard auto-regressive model for the trust index X_t^p of publisher p as evaluated on the most recently published article A_t at time step t , being dependent on the trust index as evaluated on the last L articles published by p . This is further modified by a kernel $\varphi(l)$ that weighs more recent articles more strongly, specifically a triangular kernel. The index variable l represents the lag or time delay. It quantifies the

Figure 12: Outline of our main approach

Figure 13: Alternative approach considered

temporal distance between the current observation and a previous one. Thus, X_{t-l}^p represents the value of the trust index X^p at time $t - l$, l time periods prior to the current time t .

$$\varphi(l) = \frac{2}{L} \left(1 - \frac{l-1}{L-1}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$X_t^p = \sum_{l=1}^L \varphi(l) X_{t-l}^p \quad (3)$$

In order to fit the auto-regression for each publisher p we use a linear combination of the features of the last L articles, in particular for M total features selected by both Random Forest and domain-based selection, the feature matrix $F^p \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M}$. Each row represents the features of a recent previous article while each column is one of the included feature.

$$X_t^p = \sum_{l=1}^L \varphi(l) \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m F_{lm}^p \quad (4)$$

β_m are the coefficients to be estimated for each feature m , determining how much each feature contributes to the prediction of the trust index across all considered lags. In particular the $M = 8$ features we used over the last $L = 50$ articles were:

- Bias and Objectivity Score
- Clickbait
- News alleged fake
- Number of unique links
- Discussion Score
- Bias - highly biased flag
- Bias - neutral bias flag
- Cosine Similarity

Cosine Similarity Processing For each publisher p , from the text embedding vectors of the last L articles (relative to and including the most recent article at time t) an (adjacency) matrix of pairwise cosine similarities were calculated (i.e. $50 \times 50 = 2500$ similarities). As cosine similarity is symmetric to get a monthly average, only the elements of the upper right triangle of the adjacency matrix were included in the mean. In all, the corresponding feature is

$$F_l^p = \frac{2}{L(L-1)} \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=i+1}^L sim_{\cos}(\mathbf{a}_i, \mathbf{a}_j)$$

Markov Assumption The assumption is that the previous trust index holds information from historical features. To generate a new trust index for publishers, we do not need to train the model on all historical data. Instead, we can consider the previous trust index, incorporate new features, and assign relevant weight to these parameters. This approach can be applied in future work.

Time Window versus Last Articles Initially, the auto-regression was considered to depend on the previous T time windows (e.g., the last T days, weeks, or months). However, in general, a publisher may publish sparsely and thus have too few or even no articles in such windows. Therefore, for ease and generalisation, we instead consider the last L articles, which form a minimum necessary number of articles for a publisher to gain a trust index.

Weight optimisation Equation 4 represents the mathematical model of the implemented auto-regressive models. This equation introduces some hyper-parameters to be tuned. Namely, the feature weights β_m . We are implementing basic grid search as our baseline optimisation algorithm. The following was the configuration of our experiment:

- No of Weights: No of features
- Range of Weights: [-1 to 1], so that we capture both negative and positive correlation of features to the calculated trust index.
- No of iterations: 1000

The goal of this optimisation task is to derive a configuration of feature weights such that the calculated rankings (calculated from the trust score generated from eq. (4)) are closer to the given rankings. Spearman correlation coefficient indicates the similarity between the two said rankings; the higher the coefficient, the closer the two rankings are.

Evaluation and Verification The lack of historical trust index means that the ranking of publishers is the only guide to validate our methods. The ranking provided in the `.csv` file is generated from features taken at the final time step, so evaluation can only be done at this final time step.

We therefore compare three different rankings:

- \mathcal{R}_{given} := the ranking provided in the data
- \mathcal{R}_{OS} := ranking generated solely from the bias and objectivity score in the dataset
- \mathcal{R}_{trust} := the ranking generated by our trust index

Our hypothesis is that

$$\|\mathcal{R}_{trust} - \mathcal{R}_{given}\|_s < \|\mathcal{R}_{OS} - \mathcal{R}_{given}\|_s$$

where $\|\cdot\|_s$ is defined as the difference in the Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient as discussed in Section 3.4.4. In other words, the ranking generated by our trust index aligns more closely to the ‘true’ ranking than a naive ranking based on the objectivity score.

Using the Autoregressive model, we generated rankings for publishers based on a variety of features including article clickbait flag, number of quotes, number of links, overall engagement score, news alleged fake score, discussion score, and news acknowledgement score. These rankings were compared to the expert rankings using Spearman’s rank correlation to assess how well each feature could predict the expert rankings.

The analysis was conducted across different time periods, aggregating data by month, week, and day. For each time period, rankings based on the features mentioned above were recalculated to understand how temporal granularity affects the predictive power of each feature. The

developed Autoregressive model yields the highest spearman ranking among multiple individual and combination of features (fig. 14)

Figure 14: Comparison of predicted ranking with various features and the expert ranking for news publishers on last day, week and month. The developed Autoregressive model yield the highest spearman ranking among multiple individual and combination of features

Across all time periods and features, the bias and objectivity scores consistently emerged as the best predictors of the expert rankings. This indicates that the scores capture key elements that experts consider important when ranking publishers.

- **Monthly Aggregation:** When data was aggregated by month, the objectivity and bias scores showed the highest Spearman's

correlation coefficients with the expert rankings,

- **Weekly Aggregation:** Weekly aggregated data also highlighted the objectivity and bias scores as top predictors, though with slightly lower correlation coefficients compared to the monthly aggregation.
- **Daily Aggregation:** On a daily basis, the predictive power of most features was lower, but objectivity and bias scores still outperformed other features.

4.4.2 Clustering

Given the lack of ground truth or validation (the most reliable target being the publishers’ final rankings), we considered an alternative unsupervised approach based on K-means clustering (fig. 13). In particular, the approach is to create multiple clusters based on article attributes and engagement metrics and then calculate the similarities of each publisher to those clusters on the last month of data and assign a publisher to that cluster based on maximum similarity.

Depending on trust index range the number of clusters can be formed (not publisher trust index). Clusters were created, and based on the elbow method, 28 was chosen as the value of \mathcal{K} . We classified all the features into three levels as seen in 4

Table 4: Feature Classification

Article Level Features	User Level Features	Publisher Level Features
article_bias	overall_engagement_score	bias_and_objectivity_score
article_sentiment	positive_engagement_pct	article_published_date
article_clickbait_flag	negative_engagement_pct	
article_num_quotes	neutral_engagement_pct	
article_num_links	discussion_score	
article_category	news_acknowledgement_score	
news_alleged_fake		

First, we filtered article attributes and engagement metrics from the full dataset which is merged data of all the publishers. The dataset shape is 581004, 13. The next step that we performed was to convert categorical

features into numerical features using the one hot encoding method. Some features contain null values so we dropped the rows containing null values. We scaled all these features using a standard scaler, which converted each feature to have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1.

We visualise the clusters using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) which reduced the dimensions to 2D level (fig. 15). Clusters were also visualised using the t-SNE method (fig. 16).

Figure 15: Clusters Visualisation using PCA

Figure 16: Cluster visualisation using t-SNE.

To determine the optimal number of clusters based on these features, we employed the Elbow Method. From this analysis, we decided to proceed with 28 clusters (fig. 17).

Figure 17: Elbow Method for Optimal Number of Clusters

In the next step, we created 28 clusters using the K-Means algorithm on the whole scaled dataset.

After creating the clusters, we filtered the last month of data for each publisher. We took the average of each feature group by publisher and then applied the scaling using a standard scaler.

We calculated the cosine similarity between each publisher’s last month’s data and clusters and assigned the publisher to the cluster with the highest similarity (fig. 18).

We reassigned the cluster number from the actual given Trust Index based on publisher_id, as our analysis revealed a strong average

correlation between a publisher's data from the last month and the Trust Index provided (fig. 19).

Figure 18: Publishers Clustering

Figure 19: Cluster visualisation using t-SNE.

4.4.3 Causal inference methods

Part two of the study examined the relationship between content trustworthiness and user engagement. The causal discovery approach aims to uncover the underlying causal structure between trustworthiness and engagement, while the causal inference approach focuses on quantifying the effect of trustworthiness on engagement.

Transfer Entropy for Granger causality test. Granger causality [5], is commonly adopted in causal analysis of time series data and defines causality in an information theoretic sense. In brief, if a variable X provides information in the prediction of variable Y, other than what variable Y's own history is able to provide, then we say variable X Granger

causes variable Y. Standard Granger causality tests are restricted as they only apply to linear dependence relations. In this analysis, we use bivariate transfer entropy as a measure of Granger-type causality.

The differential entropy of a random vector \mathbf{X} with values in \mathbb{R}^d .

$$h(\mathbf{X}) = - \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} p(\mathbf{x}) \ln p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (5)$$

The entropy of a discrete (multivariate) random variable $\mathbf{X} = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ can be written as:

$$H(\mathbf{X}) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p(x_i) \ln p(x_i) \quad (6)$$

where p denotes the probability mass function of X .

If $\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t, \mathbf{Z}_t$ are time series vectors, the transfer entropy of \mathbf{Y} to \mathbf{X} given \mathbf{Z} is defined as the difference between the entropy of X conditioned on its own past and the past of \mathbf{Z} , and this entropy additionally conditioned on the past of \mathbf{Y} :

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{Y} \rightarrow \mathbf{X} | \mathbf{Z}} = H(\mathbf{X} | \mathbf{X}^- \oplus \mathbf{Z}^-) - H(\mathbf{X} | \mathbf{X}^- \oplus \mathbf{Y}^- \oplus \mathbf{Z}^-) \quad (7)$$

Transfer entropy measures directed information flow from one time series variable to another. Its direct interpretation is the reduction of uncertainty (or information gain) in one time series variable when provided with information from another variable, with the result measured in units of bits or nats. When the variables are Gaussian, transfer entropy converges to standard Granger causality [2], and therefore transfer entropy can be considered as a generalised form of Granger type information theoretic causality metric. In this project, we use Shannon Entropy-based transfer entropy, with the estimation procedure of Kraskov et al. [6]. We qualitatively interpret positive transfer entropy at a specified level of statistical significance, as indicative of causal dependence.

Wavelet coherence analysis Since the time series data we have are non-stationary in nature, we also use wavelet analysis to explore this aspect. Wavelet coherence identifies the regions in time-frequency space

where two time series co-vary. While transfer entropy allows us to measure information flow at a specified time lag between two variables, wavelet analysis helps us understand how this dependence evolves over time by identifying areas of local correlation across the entire time-frequency space. In the context of this analysis, for instance, it provides additional insights into how 'forgetful' readers are regarding the quality of the content.

Matching based average causal effect estimation Building on the results from the time series causal analysis, we can focus on a specific category of articles to estimate the average effect of article bias on user engagement. To simplify the analysis, instead of using the continuous variables bias-and-objectivity-score, we use the categorical variable 'article-bias' as the treatment variable. It is interpreted as having three levels of treatment: 'Neutral' is considered the non-treatment level, 'Slightly biased' is considered treatment level 1, and 'Highly biased' is considered treatment level 2. Using standard matching techniques, we will construct balanced 'control', 'treatment level 1', and 'treatment level 2' groups.

If the exchangeability assumption holds—meaning there is no unmeasured confounding or selection bias, allowing individual articles to be considered as-if randomly assigned to one of the three groups—then we can estimate the effect of article bias on user engagement by comparing the weighted average user engagement levels across the three groups. However, this assumption is unlikely to hold in this project. Since we are examining user-content interaction, ideally, we would need measurements on both content attributes and user attributes. The absence of user-side measurements introduces the potential for confounding and selection bias. For example, if we find that articles with higher objectivity scores have more user engagement, this could simply reflect heterogeneity among consumers of the content. It could be the case that there are two sub-groups of consumers: one group inherently prefers more objective articles and tends to engage, while the other prefers the opposite. The presence of such heterogeneity introduces a selection bias problem. If left unadjusted, there is no theoretical guarantee of identifying the average causal effect.

Nonetheless, this does not imply that user-agnostic analysis is entirely uninformative. Using matching to obtain balanced sets of articles for comparing their user engagement metrics can still offer insights into the value of content from this perspective.

5 Results and Discussions

5.1 Results A: research question 1

The Trust Index calculation has been exploratory, leading us to address several minor questions along the way. The results of these inquiries have been detailed in the preceding section.

5.2 Results B: research question 2

This section presents preliminary results for research question 2 of the challenge, which explores how the trustworthiness of content relates to user engagement. The results are presented in two stages of causal analysis, moving from exploratory to confirmatory, as outlined in the Methods section.

In brief, the preliminary results suggest that significant causal dependence exists between article objectivity levels and user engagement metrics. However, this relationship is heterogeneous across contexts (e.g., different categories of articles) and dynamic over time.

The main caveat is that, given the limitations of the available data (in terms of sample size and the necessary information to adjust for confounding and selection bias), the identification of causal relationships and unbiased estimation cannot be theoretically guaranteed. Instead, we focus on qualitatively interpreting the results, drawing connections to domain knowledge, and highlighting the possibilities the results suggest. We believe more actionable insights can be drawn by extending this pipeline of analysis to a larger sample size and, ideally, with measurements on user demographics.

5.2.1 Transfer entropy results

The first step of the causal analysis is transfer entropy based Granger causality tests, sweeping across all categories of articles, and at time lags of 1 week and 2 weeks. Main results are presented in figs. 20 to 23 in the form of matrices of estimated transfer entropy values, at statistical significance level of $p < 0.1$, visualised as heatmaps. Coloured cells indicate statistically significant transfer entropy detected, with darker colours corresponding to higher transfer entropy values. In this section, we focus on qualitatively interpreting the results.

Using the examples from figs. 20 and 21, we analyse two time series: vector 1 and vector 2. We apply an information-theoretic measure of causality to determine how much additional information vector 1 provides about vector 2 beyond what is already known from the history of vector 2. Essentially, if vector 1 can predict vector 2, we say that vector 1 causes vector 2. This measure uses Shannon entropy as its unit. In the heatmap, each cell represents the transfer of entropy between an article's objectivity score and user engagement levels. The second row shows the transfer entropy between the objectivity score and negative engagement, while the third row displays the transfer entropy between the objectivity score and positive engagement. The columns represent different categories of articles. Figure 20 shows the bidirectional causality from engagement metrics to article objectivity over a lag of 1 week. This was repeated for a time-lapse of 2 weeks, as shown in figs. 22 and 23. The figure tells us that there is a positive but insignificant relationship from objectivity score to positive user engagement for politics article. In figure fig. 23, we can see that a causal relationship also exists in the opposite direction from user engagement scores to article objectivity scores.

Figure 20: Transfer entropy from article objectivity score to engagement metrics, lag=1 week

Figure 21: Transfer entropy from engagement metrics to article objectivity score, lag=1 week

Figure 22: Transfer entropy from article objectivity score to engagement metrics, lag=2 weeks

Figure 23: Transfer entropy from engagement metrics to article objectivity score, lag=2 weeks

A bidirectional relationship has been detected in a lot of categories, which may be attributed to several factors: (1) The complex nature of market interactions between users and news articles. There could indeed be a true bidirectional relationship between an article's objectivity score and the level of user engagement. (2) The potential existence of spurious causal relationships due to confounding variables. For instance, owing to sample size limitations, we were unable to further disaggregate publishers. This might act as a confounder, creating spurious causal relationships in our analysis (such as long-term trends influenced by economic conditions and the political atmosphere). (3) Spurious correlations may arise due to measurement errors in time series data, as noted by [14].

Figures 22 and 23 replicates the experiments shown in Figures 20 and 21, but with a time lag of two weeks instead of one. Upon comparison, we observe slightly less positive transfer entropy overall. This reduction may reflect the relatively short memory of users; engagement is less likely to be influenced by article quality from two weeks prior compared to just one week ago. For instance, when comparing fig. 20 and fig. 22, we note a causal relationship between objectivity scores and positive user engagement for political articles at a one-week time lag. However, this relationship is not evident at the two-week time lag.

5.2.2 Wavelet coherence results

Figures 24 to 26 present results from the wavelet coherence analysis on the dependence between the time series of weekly averaged article objectivity scores and weekly averaged user engagement metrics in 'politics' articles. The horizontal axis shows the time domain in weeks, while the vertical axis refers to frequency on a logarithmic scale. Higher frequency values (closer to the top of the axis) correspond to shorter time scales or short-term fluctuations, while lower frequency values (closer to the bottom) correspond to longer time scales or long-term trends. The warmer the colour of a region, the higher the degree of dependence between the pair of time series variables.

With the example of fig. 24, the wavelet coherence of average objectivity score and average overall engagement score, the red area at the bottom

left of the graph in the relatively low-frequency domain during weeks 0-100 (year 2020-2021) likely corresponds to the correlation between the two time series, driven by common factors such as macroeconomic trends and the presence of the COVID pandemic. The red areas of significant correlation in the relatively high-frequency domain at the top of the graph likely correspond to the type of content bias–user engagement relationship we are interested in. While earlier results from the transfer entropy test indicate an overall significant dependence between the two time series, wavelet analysis shows that this relationship can be dynamic over time.

Figure 24: Wavelet coherence, politics, objectivity score vs overall engagement

Wavelet coherence: Politics, obj score vs positive engagement

Figure 25: Wavelet coherence, politics, objectivity score vs positive engagement

Wavelet coherence: Politics, obj score vs negative engagement

Figure 26: Wavelet coherence, politics, objectivity score vs negative engagement

5.2.3 Matching based estimation results

Figure 27: Log overall-engagement-score in constructed comparison groups, politics articles

Following the time series causal analysis, we focus on the association between article bias and user engagement in 'politics' articles. As introduced in the Methods section, we use the categorical variable 'article bias' as the treatment variable. There are three levels of treatment: 'Neutral' as the non-treatment level, 'Slightly biased' as treatment level 1, and 'Highly biased' as treatment level 2. Using standard matching techniques, we construct balanced 'control', 'treatment level 1', and 'treatment level 2' groups, and compare the user engagement scores across the three groups. Figure 27 presents the distribution of overall user engagement score across the three groups.

Due to the limited sample size and the lack of user demographics to adjust for selection bias, we do not have sufficient grounds to rigorously justify the results as unbiased estimations of causal effects. However, the results

interestingly indicate that for 'politics' articles, more biased articles may be associated with higher average user engagement scores. This observation adds further motivation to develop this line of inquiry and better understand user behaviour in relation to content quality and the trustworthiness of the publisher.

5.3 Discussion

5.3.1 Causal analysis

While we are combining both information theoretic approaches to causal analysis and canonical forms of cause-effect analysis, the two approaches to causal modelling stems from very different yet connected conceptions of causality. In a nutshell, the information theoretic point of view defines causation as directed information flow between dynamic processes. In comparison, the cause-effect (potential outcomes) framework adopts a counterfactual dependence point of view to define causation. Therefore, the two approaches offer complementary insights into how content quality and user engagement are dependent on each other.

5.4 Limitations

5.4.1 Trust index construction

With very limited validation data or an externally derived notion of "trustworthiness"—itself a very difficult term to define in any context—the construction of a measure of trustworthiness requires far more domain expertise.

The different approaches presented in this report are not rigorous formal definitions of a trust index, and yet, as a data-scientific approach, they relied on very sparse validation. For instance, the final ranking of publisher trustworthiness by domain experts was deemed the most reliable or reasonable validation; however, by its very nature, this existed only at the temporal end of the dataset. The bias and objectivity score is available for each article, but in using this as the target variable, it cannot therefore be used as a feature in the calculation of future trust

indices.

Moreover, without the full textual content of articles, it was difficult to produce any 'common sense' or intuitive validation, such as correlating a constructed trust index with the frequency of certain words and phrases typically associated with fake news.

5.4.2 Causal analysis

Recall that we have presented two steps of causal analysis. In both steps, the robustness of the analyses is constrained by the data available. In summary:

Larger sample size For bivariate time series causality tests, more samples are needed to construct longer and more granular time series variables. More contextual variables are needed to control for confounding by global trends, such as economic conditions.

User demographics As discussed in the Methods section, since we are probing user-content interaction, ideally, we would need measurements on both content attributes and user attributes to sufficiently adjust for confounding and selection bias in the estimation of causal effect. Based on the analysis so far, we cannot conclude that raising the level of article content trustworthiness will lead to an increase in user engagement. If we had measurements of, for example, average user age or other demographic characteristics, we might be able to alleviate the heterogeneity to a certain degree and strengthen the causal interpretation of the analysis.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

This challenge set out to answer two key questions: whether a dynamic trust index for publishers can be developed, and whether a higher trust index leads to more positive user engagement. The findings suggest that bias and objectivity scores are crucial predictors of publisher rankings across different time periods, with the publisher's last month of data

showing a strong correlation with the Trust Index. Additionally, there is evidence of causal relationships between content quality and user engagement, although these relationships are heterogeneous and vary over time. Next, we present some possible future directions for this project.

6.1 Level of analysis and degrees of disaggregation

In the challenge, we attempted to create a publisher-level trust index. In business settings, it might be more informative to construct trust indices at a more granular level. For example, a trust index could be publisher-category specific, so that if used for pricing, it becomes a more precise reflection of the content's quality.

Similarly, the analysis could be repeated with a larger sample size to obtain more robust results. For example, in the time-series-related analysis, being able to conduct disaggregated analysis at daily intervals, differentiated by publisher, would remove spurious causation due to measurement problems.

6.2 Data imputation

In relation to restricted data size, it is worth considering generating realistic synthetic datasets to lend more statistical power and precision to the analyses.

6.3 Back-prediction and trust index

Recall that we have taken a semi-supervised approach to obtain a model for the trust index with limited data. It would be a meaningful exercise to back-predict the historical values of the trust index and examine its behaviour. This is also a common approach in some fields of scientific research facing similar challenges; for example, in the study of ancient climate (palaeo-climate), where mechanistic models are built from a combination of domain knowledge and a small set of recent observations of Earth's climate.

7 Team members

Figure 28: The Data Study Group participants, facilitators, PI and Challenge Owner.

Jacques Bara is a Ph.D. in Mathematics of Real-World Systems from the University of Warwick and incoming Postdoctoral Fellow at the University of Bonn. He works in multi-agent dynamics and multi-agent reinforcement learning. He contributed to the text-embedding analysis and the autoregressive model theory. He was also one of the two facilitators of the group.

Riya Chhikara is a Data Scientist at The Economist, specialising in Explainable AI and the detection of fake news within the media industry. She holds a Master's degree in Applied Social Data Science from the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE). In this project, Riya contributed to the Exploratory Data Analysis and the analysis of text-embedding vectors to support the model's development.

Jesus de la Fuente Cedeño is a Ph.D. student at the University of Navarra, who works at the intersection of Machine Learning and

Computational Biology. His main area of research is representation learning, graph learning and explainable AI applied to the fields of drug discovery and digital cytometry. He contributed to the design and implementation of the AR model for building the trust index, the analysis of the Spearman correlation for evaluating publisher rankings and the feature selection process through tree ensemble modelling (random forest).

Iqra jilani is a second year PhD student at Coventry University, who is working on improving energy access to refugee camps using machine learning. She contributed to automatic weight specifications, for given autoregressive models, using the tuning methods. It helped in setting the weights such that the predicting rankings are closer to given rankings.

Sokipriala Jonah is a Ph.D. researcher from the Centre for Computational Science and Mathematical Modelling at Coventry University. His research focuses on the design of next-generation wireless sensor networks using reinforcement learning and federated learning. He contributed to the analysis of feature importance and the Spearman's rank correlation section.

Shivani Khandelwal is a Master's by Research Student at Coventry University, UK. Her research focuses on building an optimal controller for the heating and cooling systems of buildings using data-driven methods and reinforcement learning to reduce energy consumption and cost. She contributed to Markov assumption and Method 2 section 4.4.2 Clustering approach to find the Trust Index of the publisher using K-means.

Emma Li is a PhD researcher from the UKRI CDT in Accountable, Responsible and Transparent AI at the University of Bath. Her research is on improving multimodal representation learning techniques with the aim of explainability. She contributed to the exploratory data analysis, and the theory and design of the autoregressive model.

Kaitlyn Louth is a Ph.D. researcher from The Maxwell Institute Graduate School at The University of Edinburgh and Heriot-Watt University. Her research involves building critical illness risk prediction models using Bayesian networks and multilevel modelling. She contributed to the exploratory data analysis, analysis of the text-embedding vector, and

specifically the cosine similarity investigation.

Jing (Mirah) Zhang is a Ph.D. candidate and research associate in Geographic Data Science at the University of Bristol. She works on causal modeling with geographic data. She contributed to discussions on the auto-regressive model, and the implementation and write up of research question 2. She was also a facilitator on this challenge.

Maryleen Amaizu received a Ph.D. in Computer Science from the University of Leicester, focusing on performance-efficient and privacy-preserving machine learning systems for resource-contained environments. Her research interests are centered around creating robust and reliable frameworks that enable intelligent models to operate effectively. In this project, she served as the Principal Investigator (PI), leading the preparatory work, including the ethics and Turing-ZZAZZ relationship, and edited the final report.

Madhusudhanan Krishnamoorthy heads AI capabilities in ZZAZZ. He is responsible for fulfilling business objectives via AI starting from algorithmic refinement to ML model deployment and post-performance assessment. He is an accomplished AI professional previously served as the Principal Applied and Data Scientist at Microsoft, specialising in Knowledge Mining and Inference. With an impressive 19.5 years of total experience, including 11 years in leadership roles focusing on data and AI, Madhusudhanan has proven to be a visionary and customer-centric advocate. Beyond his official assignments, Madhusudhanan is an innovation evangelist, contributing to ongoing Ph.D. research in IIIT Hyderabad on Spiking Neural Networks via Neuromorphic hardware. His commitment to innovation is underscored by his leadership in patent filings and contributions to diverse thematic areas, reflecting wide-ranging expertise.

Harshit Sharma is a data science professional and the Lead AI Scientist at ZZAZZ. He has 5 years of experience in the Data science industry spanning across Fintech, gaming and Pricing. He was responsible for formulating the DSG ZZAZZ challenge, data curation and played a crucial role in brainstorming phase of the challenge.

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